

THE IMPORTANCE OF INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS AND THE ROLE OF FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTORS IN THE GROWTH OF THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY

¹Navruzov Ikram
Abdullaevich

¹Senior teacher of the department of “Evaluation work and investments” of Tashkent State University of Economics. Uzbekistan, Tashkent.

Annotation

The article creating a positive investment climate should not be interpreted as a key process in the globalization of the economy, and as a result, the expansion of access to investment resources, which in turn will increase competition among investors. If we want to increase the volume of foreign investment, it is necessary to increase the investment potential of enterprises, regional conditions and conditions to a more acceptable and higher level than others (competitors), as well as to stimulate domestic (national) investment. we need to focus on ensuring that it is holistic.

Key words:

enterprise risk, investment potential of the enterprise, investment climate, innovation in enterprises, small business entities, innovation, investment process.

1. Introduction.

The more favorable the investment climate, the lower the entrepreneurial risk of the investor, and this will increase the influx of investors. Conversely, the more unfavorable the investment climate, the higher the risk. This will increase the cost to the recipient of the investment. The state of the investment environment is important not only for the investor but also for the investor [1]. A number of such cases require a series of measures to improve the existing mechanism for attracting foreign investment to the country's economy and increase its efficiency in ensuring the competitiveness of national enterprises. In turn, the process of ensuring the competitiveness of national enterprises by attracting foreign investment in the country's economy is multifactorial integration. Therefore, a

methodological approach to indicators that assess the competitiveness of the national economy is required in this regard.

The analysis of the socio-economic changes taking place in our country shows that the modernization of the economy and the role of active investment policy are very important in the achievements and successes. Accordingly, it is important to create an effective system of enterprises, to study the theoretical and methodological basis for assessing the attractiveness of their investment climate and potential.

2. Literature review.

The investment attractiveness of enterprises depends on the country's investment policy and the created investment climate. In particular, the investment climate is considered

as a system of three elements: investment potential, investment risk and legal conditions [2].

Considering the factors influencing the formation of a favorable investment climate in the country/region, it should be noted that it is important for the country to be integrated in the world community in terms of investment attractiveness. The strategy of increasing the country's investment prestige is important for attracting foreign direct investment [3].

Interpretation of “investment potential” as a set of investment resources, consisting of part of the accumulated capital, expressed in the form of investment demand in the investment market, which has the potential to become a real investment demand that meets the material, financial and intellectual needs of capital reproduction reaches [4].

The attractiveness of the investment climate, the economic development of each region depends on the potential of capital and labor resources, the level of their use. It is generally accepted that the economic potential of a region and its potential is determined by the production of vital goods through the efficient use of all the complex resources available there [5].

3. Research methodology.

The role of foreign investment in ensuring the competitiveness of enterprises, the classification of risks affecting the activities of the enterprise, as well as scientific proposals and practical recommendations for improvement

through the methods of systematic analysis were formed.

4. Analysis and discussion of results.

In the current socio-economic environment, the inflow of investment depends on the development of innovative industries and the development of innovative entrepreneurship, the investment climate and the investment mechanism.

In a study of regional economics, the study grouped the factors that determine the investment attractiveness of the regions into a single system. It summarizes and classifies the views and scientific-practical views that represent the socio-economic potential of the region, reflecting the complex indicators as the main groups.

As a result of the active work of various factors of the investment potential of the above-mentioned enterprise, this concentration will allow the active inflow of foreign investment. And that, of course, creates more jobs, more income, more opportunities for economic growth. In addition, the most important thing is that foreign investors not only bring capital into the business, but also bring advanced knowledge and experience from their home countries. This will allow the country to grow economically in the future.

Innovation is seen as a necessary tool for sustaining economic growth and competitiveness in traditional and new high-capacity industries (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Basic features of innovation and stages of innovation [6]

Investment in manufacturing and services in a small competitive environment implies the organization of production on the basis of the use of new techniques and technologies, new, previously unused types of services in the field of services. The concept of

innovation also means the production of new special products, which replace the existing products with new special types. It also means launching a new product, a new market, based on the use of new techniques and technologies in a highly competitive environment.

Table 1

Rating of innovative activities of developed countries of 2021 [7]

N.	Countries	Innovation inputs	Innovation outputs	Knowledge creation	Investment	Production and export complexity
1.	Germany	14	9	5	60	4
2.	China	25	7	4	2	1
3.	USA	3	4	3	1	2
4.	Italy	33	25	7	9	15
5.	India	57	45	13	32	18

The table above shows the ranking of Germany, China, the United States, Italy and India in terms of innovation potential, while the United States ranks 4th in terms of innovation results. The U.S. states are directly in 3rd place. America is also at the forefront of investment inflows and outflows. In terms of export potential, China ranks 1st, and 4th in terms of creating new knowledge, intangible assets and inventions.

As you can see in the picture above, the number of foreign shareholders in the stock market of Uzbekistan in 2022 reached 3321, of which 328 are legal entities and 2993 are individuals. It is obvious that as a result of foreign investment in the stock market of Uzbekistan, along with the direct increase in the volume of production of enterprises, the share price of the enterprise in the secondary market will increase significantly.

The socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its becoming one of the most competitive countries in the world is closely linked with the investment policy of the country, the region and its economic sectors, as

well as the investment attractiveness of individual enterprises.

The state of the state budget directly affects the development of the stock market. If the expenditure in the budget exceeds the income and a deficit occurs, and this deficit is covered by money emission, this situation leads to an increase in the inflation rate. As a result, investing in the stock market slows down.

Also, in the experience of many developed countries and the first years of our republic's independence, the method of covering the budget deficit in non-inflationary ways is directly related to the activity of the stock market.

Of course, it is a good indicator that investors from foreign countries carry out investment activities within the country. However, the majority of foreign capital-based businesses are in Tashkent, Tashkent region and Samarkand region. It is clear that the distribution of joint ventures by sector and industry has also led to disparities.

Recognizing the importance of the role of foreign direct investment in increasing the

investment attractiveness of our country, a number of measures are being taken to attract these investments. Attracting and fully utilizing foreign direct investment contributes to the growth of employment and living standards in the country, improving the income of the population, increasing the investment attractiveness of our country in the international arena.

In the current context of developing a market economy, increasing the country's investment attractiveness is one of the most important indicators of capital inflows into the country. Policies to increase investment attractiveness also play an important role in attracting foreign direct investment to the country. “Economic growth is achieved primarily through the creation of competitive industrial chains and increased investment in such projects. At the same time, it is necessary to reduce public participation in investment policy and increase the share of private and direct investment” [8]. Therefore, the study of foreign direct investment is important to increase investment attractiveness.

The above figures show the indicators of foreign direct investment and loans in the framework of investment projects by region (Figure 6). It should be noted that in 2021, the use of foreign direct investment and loans will be several times higher than in 2018. At the same time, we can see that our country has an active policy of attracting foreign direct investment and loans from international financial institutions. This shows that the volume of investment in the country's economy is growing from year to year. The improvement of the investment climate of enterprises operating in our country can be seen in the share of investments in fixed assets in the table above, which is reflected in the table above.

5. Conclusions and suggestions.

Innovation strategy is formed based on the organizational, production, technological,

managerial and other structural potential of the enterprise. Innovation strategies differ in their scope, timing, areas, and directions. The innovation strategy is based on the company's own capabilities and the market infrastructure capabilities of the economy. In many cases, the innovation strategy is shaped by the general environment of the economy, the state of the free competitive environment, the state of industries and sectors, production, technological, entrepreneurial potential and existing opportunities. The fact that the enterprise is organized on a competitive basis encourages it to develop one or another innovation strategy. The formulation of the innovation strategy is shaped as an innovation project as mentioned above [10].

- development of programs for the targeted use of foreign investment for the full use of the territorial export potential and others.

- optimizing the relationship between investors and the government to completely eliminate bureaucratic barriers and restrictions in the implementation of investment projects through digitalization and remote provision of public services;

- improving the system of attracting foreign investment in the implementation of strategically important projects, deepening the localization of production and expanding inter-sectoral industrial cooperation, economic growth and structural transformation of the economy;

- creating a favorable business environment based on high technology and creating high value-added joint projects;

Based on the above scientific suggestions and recommendations, their in-depth study, analysis and substantiation will yield results in the near future. It will also have a positive effect on increasing the country's investment attractiveness by creating a favorable investment climate in the country.

6. Literatura/Reference:

1. Elvira Sojli, Wing Wah Tham. “The Impact of Foreign Government Investments: Sovereign Wealth Fund Investments in the United States” In Institutional Investors in Global Capital Markets. Published online: 8 March 2015; 207-243. www.scopus.com
2. Takhumova Oksana V., Kasatkina Elena V., Masliхова Elena A, Alexey V.Yumashev, Maria V.Yumasheva. The main directions of increasing the investment attractiveness of the Russian regions in the conditions of institutional transformations. // Revista ESPACIOS, Vol. 39 (Number 37) 2018. – P.12;
3. Smaglyukova T. M. general approaches to the formation of regional investment policy // Modern problems of science. - 2014. - No. 1.
4. Tumusov F.S. Investment potential of the region: theory, problems, practice. - M., “Economics”, 1999. 272-page.
5. Akerman Ye.N., Mixalchuk A. A., Trifanov A. Yu. Typology of regions as a tool for co-organization of regional development // Bulletin of the Tomsk State University. un-a. Economy. No. 331. 126–131-p.
6. Butaev J., Radjabov U. The tax system as a structural link of the financial system //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 11. – №. 4. – C. 1770-1780.
7. Butaev J. THE IMPACT OF THE CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC ON THE GLOBAL ECONOMY: ANALYSIS, FORECASTS AND CONCLUSIONS //Студенческий вестник. – 2020. – №. 43-7. – C. 32-35.
8. Butaev J., Ochilov B. The role of the investment environment in attracting foreign investment //ASIAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDIMENSIONAL RESEARCH. – 2021. – T. 10. – №. 5. – C. 687-697.
9. Tursunkulovich S. R., Bakhtiyorovich O. B. Some using questions instruments of monetary policy //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 3. – C. 211-216.
10. Abdullaevich N. I. Foreign Experiences of Attracting Foreign Direct Investments //The Peerian Journal. – 2023. – T. 22. – C. 46-50.